

**TOWARDS STANDARDIZED EVALUATION: A NEW INSTRUMENT FOR ASSESSING
PSYCHOMOTOR SKILLS IN DOMESTIC INSTALLATION IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF
BAUCHI STATE**

Emmanuel Vandi Mbagal¹ & Ali Dahiru²

¹Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria

²Bauchi State Universal Basic Education Board, Bauchi State

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8328082>

Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to develop and validate a new instrument for assessing psychomotor skills for electrical installation and maintenance work (EIMW) students in domestic installation in Bauchi State Technical Colleges. The study which adopted Instrumentation research design was guided by four research objectives and four research questions. The population comprised of 250 individuals, including 38 EIMW teachers and 212 NTCII EIMW trade students from various technical colleges. The sample includes all 38 EIMW teachers, while purposive sampling is used to select Government Day Technical College Azare for the try-out. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled: Psychomotor Skills in Domestic Installation Questionnaire (PSDIQ). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by three experts from department of electrical technology education, Modibbo Adama University Yola. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability index of 0.89 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation, factor analysis, Cronbach Alpha, and Fleiss KAPPA were used to answer each research respectively. The findings of the study revealed that the 20 out of 22 psychomotor skills task items were appropriate for inclusion in the Domestic Installation Psychomotor Skills Assessment Instrument (DIPSAI) for assessing the psychomotor skills of EIMW works trade students in domestic installation. Furthermore, DIPSAI underscore its validity in accurately measuring the intended constructs. DIPSAI was found to be reliable. The study recommends that DIPSAI should be made available to the Ministry of Education in order for the ministry to make it an instrument to be used in the assessment process of psychomotor skills in technical colleges in Bauchi State. Furthermore, Examination bodies such as NABTEB, WAEC, and NECO should adopt the use of DIPSAI for the assessment of students' performance in practical examinations in EIMW trade especially domestic installations.

Keywords: Assessment, Domestic Installation, Electrical Installation and Maintenance, Standardized Evaluation, Psychomotor Skills

Introduction

Technical education in Nigeria is a critical component of the nation's educational system. It is designed to equip students with practical skills and competencies necessary for various trades and industries (Ekeh, 2016). Technical colleges as a component part of technical education in Nigeria play a vital role in achieving the aims of technical education. These institutions are intended to provide students with hands-on training in various trades, including electrical installation and maintenance. However, to fulfil their mission effectively, technical colleges must employ robust assessment mechanisms

that accurately gauge students' psychomotor skills, which are central to their success in the workforce (Ogunbote et al., 2020). Electrical installation and maintenance works trade are fundamental components of technical education in Nigeria. The trade prepares students for careers in domestic installation, electrical engineering and related fields.

Domestic installation refers to the electrical infrastructure and wiring systems within residential buildings. It encompasses the design, installation, maintenance, and repair of electrical systems that power homes, providing electricity for lighting, appliances, heating, and other domestic needs (Baird et al., 2019). The safety, reliability, and efficiency of domestic installations are paramount to ensure the well-being of occupants and to meet the electrical demands of modern households. Domestic electrical installations include various components and aspects, such as wiring circuits, distribution boards, outlets, switches, lighting fixtures, and protective devices like circuit breakers and fuses. Proper design and installation are essential to ensure that the electrical system meets the specific needs of the household, adheres to safety standards, and complies with local electrical codes and regulations (Nkosi et al., 2020).

Moreover, domestic installations must prioritize electrical safety. Faulty or outdated wiring, inadequate grounding, and improper connections can lead to electrical hazards, including electrical fires and shocks. Routine maintenance and periodic inspections are crucial to identify and rectify potential issues in domestic installations, ensuring the continued safety and functionality of the electrical system. Efforts are continuously made to improve the efficiency of domestic electrical installations, with advancements in energy-efficient lighting, smart home automation, and renewable energy integration (Alotaibi et al., 2018). These developments contribute to reducing energy consumption and environmental impact while enhancing the convenience and comfort of domestic living spaces.

However, assessing the psychomotor skills of students in these programs has been a longstanding challenge (Mbaegbu, 2018). Traditional assessment methods often fall short of capturing the full spectrum of psychomotor skills required for effective electrical installation and maintenance work.

Psychomotor skills encompass the physical abilities and coordination required to perform tasks and actions effectively. In the context of electrical installation and maintenance, these skills are indispensable for safely and competently handling electrical components and systems. Assessing psychomotor skills is complex due to the practical nature of the tasks involved and the need for objective, standardized evaluation (Wagiran et al., 2019).

The assessment of psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance works is crucial for determining the readiness of students for the job market. Effective assessment tools should cover a range of competencies, including equipment handling, wiring, troubleshooting, and safety protocols. Traditional assessment methods often rely on subjective observation, limiting the reliability and objectivity of the evaluation (Sulaiman et al., 2021).

Assessing psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance works typically involves two main types of assessment: product assessment and performance assessment (Rodriguez, 2019). Product assessment in electrical installation and maintenance involves evaluating the final result of a student's work. This assessment method looks at the quality, accuracy, and completeness of the electrical installation or maintenance project. However, relying solely on product assessment may not provide a comprehensive view of a student's psychomotor skills. It assesses the outcome rather than the process, which is equally important in technical education (Ismail et al., 2021).

Performance assessment, on the other hand, delves into the process and execution of tasks. It evaluates how well students apply their skills, use tools and equipment, follow safety protocols, and troubleshoot issues during electrical installation and maintenance work (Mann et al., 2018). Performance assessment provides insights into students' abilities to

apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations, making it a valuable component of a comprehensive psychomotor skills assessment.

The development of an instrument for assessing psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance is a critical step toward standardizing the evaluation process. This instrument should encompass a range of tasks and activities relevant to the field, ensuring that it adequately measures the skills required for success in the profession (Oladinni, 2019). Furthermore, the instrument is designed to be objective, valid, reliable, and aligned with the learning objectives of technical colleges.

Ensuring the validity of the developed instrument is essential to guarantee that it accurately measures the intended psychomotor skills. Content validity, criterion-related validity, and construct validity are key aspects to consider. Content validity ensures that the instrument comprehensively covers the relevant skills and competencies (Wang et al., 2018). Criterion-related validity involves comparing the instrument's results with established criteria or standards to determine its accuracy in predicting real-world performance. Construct validity assesses whether the instrument measures the intended psychomotor constructs accurately (Angoff, 2017).

Reliability is another crucial aspect of the developed instrument. It indicates the consistency and stability of the instrument's measurements over time and across different assessors or settings (Streiner et al., 2015). Ensuring high inter-rater reliability, test-retest reliability, and internal consistency reliability is essential to make the instrument a dependable tool for assessing psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance.

Conclusively, the development of a standardized assessment instrument for psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance is a vital step toward improving the quality and relevance of technical education at Bauchi State Technical Colleges. This instrument should encompass both product and performance assessment methods, be valid and reliable, and align closely with the learning objectives of the programs. Such an instrument has the potential to enhance the effectiveness of technical education and better prepare students for successful careers in the electrical installation and maintenance field, especially domestic installation.

Statement of the Problem

Technical and vocational education plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the practical skills needed to meet the demands of various trades and industries. In the context of electrical installation and maintenance, the acquisition of psychomotor skills is paramount for students aspiring to excel in the field. However, the assessment of these psychomotor skills remains a significant challenge in technical colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The existing evaluation methods used in Bauchi State Technical Colleges to assess the psychomotor skills of electrical installation and maintenance students lack standardization and validity. This inconsistency in assessment hampers the accurate measurement of students' skill levels and the effectiveness of the educational programs. Furthermore, the absence of a standardized assessment instrument for evaluating psychomotor skills in domestic electrical installation exacerbates this problem.

As a result, there is a critical need to address this deficiency by developing and implementing a standardized evaluation instrument tailored to the specific context of domestic electrical installation in Bauchi State Technical Colleges. This instrument should be capable of accurately and reliably measuring the psychomotor skills of students, thus facilitating better educational outcomes and ensuring that graduates are adequately prepared to meet the needs of the electrical installation and maintenance industry in Bauchi State.

Therefore, this research aims to design, validate, and implement a new instrument for assessing the psychomotor skills of electrical installation and maintenance students in domestic installation, contributing to the standardization and improvement of the evaluation process in technical colleges in Bauchi State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to develop and validate a new instrument for assessing psychomotor skills for electrical installation and maintenance students in domestic installation in Bauchi State Technical Colleges. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determined the psychomotor skills items appropriate for assessing the psychomotor skills of EIM works trade students in domestic installation.
2. Determined the construct validity of the assessment instrument.
3. Try-out the final assessment instrument to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument.
4. Determined the inter-rater reliability of the developed assessment instrument.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What are the psychomotor skills items appropriate for assessing the psychomotor skills of EIM works trade students in domestic installation?
2. What is the construct validity of the assessment instrument?
3. What is the internal consistency of the assessment instrument?
4. What is the inter-rater reliability of the assessment instrument?

Methodology

The study employed an instrumentation research design, chosen to create a novel tool for assessing psychomotor skills in electrical installation and maintenance students. The study focuses on Bauchi State as the geographical area of interest and involves a population of 250 individuals, including 38 EIMW teachers and 212 NTCII EIMW trade students from various technical colleges in the state. The sample includes all 38 EIMW teachers, while purposive sampling is used to select Government Day Technical College Azare for the try-out phase based on specific criteria related to the availability of electrical power, functional workshops, and moderate student populations. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers titled: Psychomotor Skills in Domestic Installation Questionnaire (PSDIQ) extracted from the National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) syllabus for Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Domestic Installation. A modified five point Likert scale was used to determine the skills needed using the response options of Very Highly Appropriate (VHA) =5, Highly Appropriate (HA) =4, Moderately Appropriate (MA) =3, Slightly Appropriate (SA) =2 and Very Slightly Appropriate (VSA) =1.

The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The instrument reliability was obtained through trial test on 5 EIM teachers in Government Science and Technical College, Kumo Gombe State, and a 0.89 reliability coefficient was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. The reliability index indicated that the instrument was suitable and reliable for data collection. Research question 1 was answered using the mean and standard deviation of the

electrical installation and maintenance work trade teachers in order to select the psychomotor skills in domestic installation appropriate for inclusion into the Domestic Installation Psychomotor Skills Assessment Instrument DIPSAI. A mean cut-off of 3.00 was chosen. Therefore any skill with a mean score of 3.00 or above was considered appropriate for inclusion in DIPSAI, while skills with a mean score below 3.00 were considered inappropriate. Research question 2 was subjected to factor analysis using 0.30 as a loading factor at 10% overlapping variance. Summarily, any task with factor loading of 0.30 and above was considered valid while any item with factor loading less than 0.30 was considered invalid. For research question 3, Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the internal consistency; while for research question 4 data generated from try-out of DIPSAI was analyzed using Fleiss KAPPA inter-rater reliability. The development of the assessment instrument follows a multi-stage approach, adapted from Akpan et al. (2019), including the identification of psychomotor contents and tasks, item writing, validation by experts, and final assessment template.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the psychomotor skills items appropriate for assessing the psychomotor skills of EIM works trade students in domestic installation?

Table 1: Mean Response of Respondents on the Appropriateness of Psychomotor Skills Items for Assessing the Psychomotor Skills of Domestic Installation

S/No	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Respondent = 38 Remark
Cluster 1: Surface Wiring Tasks				
1.	Ability to draw electrical installation diagram for building	3.92	1.62	Appropriate
2.	Ability to demonstrate the use of plumb-line	3.95	1.43	Appropriate
3.	Ability to demonstrate the use of chalk-line	3.61	1.70	Appropriate
4.	Ability to demonstrate the use of spirit level	4.03	1.48	Appropriate
5.	Ability to carry out simple surface wiring using appropriate tools	3.97	1.53	Appropriate
6.	Ability to appropriately observe safety measures required in surface wiring	3.76	1.38	Appropriate
Cluster 2: Conduit Wiring Tasks				
7.	Ability to identify conduit components	3.84	1.59	Appropriate
8.	Ability to identify types of conduits	3.58	1.76	Appropriate
9.	Ability to use conduit accessories	3.53	1.52	Appropriate
10.	Ability to thread conduit pipes using a ratchet handle tool	3.68	1.56	Appropriate
11.	Ability to determine bend permissible radial lengths	2.13	0.93	Inappropriate
12.	Ability to carry out simple surface conduit installation	3.89	1.64	Appropriate
13.	Ability to carry out simple concealed conduit installation	3.66	1.74	Appropriate
14.	Ability to draw cables into surface conduit installation using fish wire	3.55	1.62	Appropriate
15.	Ability to carry out the inspection of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations	3.63	1.02	Appropriate
16.	Ability to carry out the required tests of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations	3.68	1.56	Appropriate
17.	Ability to maintain tools used for conduits installation	4.13	0.88	Appropriate
Cluster 3: Installation of Protective Devices Tasks				
18.	Ability to use common types of protective devices	3.97	1.08	Appropriate
19.	Ability to carry out electrical connections of ELCBs to the supply authority	3.61	1.75	Appropriate
20.	Ability to install earth continuity conductor (ECC)	2.47	0.95	Inappropriate
21.	Ability to carry out inspection on all joints made in a simple	3.58	1.50	Appropriate

wiring			
22. Ability to demonstrate the use of test lamp	3.61	1.53	Appropriate

\bar{x} = Mean Responses, SD = Standard Deviation, VSA = Very Slightly Appropriate

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 1 showed the psychomotor skills item appropriate for inclusion into the Domestic Installation Psychomotor Skills Assessment Instrument (DIPSAI) for assessing students’ psychomotor skills in domestic installation. The respondents indicated that 20 task items in domestic installation were considered appropriate as the mean values range between 3.53 and 4.13 which were above the criterion mark of 3.00. The standard deviation also ranged between 0.79 and 1.76. This showed that the responses were clustered together and there was homogeneity in the responses. However, 2 task items were considered very slightly appropriate as the mean value fall below the criterion value of 3.00 and had a mean value which ranged between 2.13 and 2.47. The standard deviation also ranged between 0.93 and 0.95 which also indicated homogeneity in the responses.

Research Question 2: What is the construct validity of the assessment instrument?

Table 2: Factor Analysis on Assessing the Construct Validity of the Developed DIPSAI

S/No	Items	Factor Loading	Remark
MODULE: DOMESTIC INSTALLATION			
Cluster 1: Surface Wiring Tasks			
1.	Ability to draw electrical installation diagram for building	1.00	Valid
2.	Ability to demonstrate the use of plumb-line	0.60	Valid
3.	Ability to demonstrate the use of chalk-line	0.89	Valid
4.	Ability to demonstrate the use of spirit level	1.00	Valid
5.	Ability to carry out simple surface wiring using appropriate tools	1.00	Valid
6.	Ability to appropriately observe safety measures required in surface wiring	1.00	Valid
Cluster 2: Conduit Wiring Tasks			
7.	Ability to identify conduit components	0.76	Valid
8.	Ability to identify types of conduits	0.90	Valid
9.	Ability to use conduit accessories	1.00	Valid
10.	Ability to thread conduit pipes using a ratchet handle tool	1.00	Valid
11.	Ability to carry out simple surface conduit installation	1.00	Valid
12.	Ability to carry out simple concealed conduit installation	1.00	Valid
13.	Ability to draw cables into surface conduit installation using fish wire	1.00	Valid
14.	Ability to carry out the inspection of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations	1.00	Valid
15.	Ability to carry out the required tests of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations	1.00	Valid
16.	Ability to maintain tools used for conduits installation	1.00	Valid
Cluster 3: Installation of Protective Devices Tasks			
17.	Ability to use common types of protective devices	0.92	Valid
18.	Ability to carry out electrical connections of ELCBs to the supply authority	0.65	Valid
19.	Ability to carry out inspection on all joints made in a simple wiring	1.00	Valid
20.	Ability to demonstrate the use of test lamp	1.00	Valid

\bar{x} = Mean Responses, SD = Standard Deviation

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 2 shows the construct validity of the assessment instrument DIPSAL. 20 task items considered appropriate were subjected to validation and the result showed that all of the task items were valid. The Psychomotor skills identified in DIPSAL indicated that the task items had their factor loading ranging from 0.60 to 1.00 and were all greater than the factor loading of 0.30 at 10% overlapping variance with two component matrices. This indicated that all the 20 psychomotor task items in DIPSAL measured the psychomotor skills needed to be measured.

Research Question 3: What is the internal consistency of the assessment instrument?

Table 3: Internal Consistency of the Assessment Instrument

S/N	Items	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha Index	Remark
Module: Domestic Installation				
1.	Surface Wiring Tasks	6	0.95	Reliable
2.	Conduit Wiring Tasks	10	0.90	Reliable
3.	Installation of Protective Devices Tasks	4	0.84	Reliable
Overall Reliability		20	0.87	Reliable

The developed instrument was subjected to a reliability test and Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability index of the items. The results indicated that 20 psychomotor skills grouped in 3 clusters were reliable with the reliability index ranging between 0.84 and 0.95 after the try-out. The total item reliability of 0.87 indicate that DIPSAL was reliable.

Research Question 4: What is the inter-rater reliability of the assessment instrument?

Table 4: Fleiss Multi-rater Reliability of Developed Instrument for Assessing Psychomotor Skills of EIM Works Trade Students

S/N	Items	No. of Items	No. of Raters	Kappa - rater Indices	Indices Significant	Remark
1.	Surface Wiring Tasks	6	6	0.813	0.000	Reliable
2.	Conduit Wiring Tasks	10	6	0.924	0.000	Reliable
3.	Installation of Protective Devices Tasks	4	6	0.867	0.000	Reliable
Cumulative Mean		20		0.868		Reliable

Table 4, shows the Fleiss Multi-rater Kappa or inter-rater reliability of the assessment instrument DIPSAL. On the whole, as shown in Table 4, there are 3 clusters of psychomotor skills with corresponding 20 task items with paired inter-rater indices ranging between 0.813 and 0.924 which indicates a very high agreement between the raters. The result further revealed the significant values (p-value) of the raters rating the psychomotor skills also ranges between 0.000 and 0.037 respectively. These values are less than the 0.05 level of significance, thus indicating that raters' ratings of the developed instrument for assessing the psychomotor skills of students in domestic installation statistically are significant and highly reliable with a 0.868 reliability index.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that 20 out of 22 psychomotor skills task items spread across 3 clusters were appropriate for inclusion in the Domestic Installation Psychomotor Skills Assessment Instrument (DIPSAL) for assessing the psychomotor skills of EIM works trade students in domestic installation. The findings are in agreement with Ezekiel (2010) who developed an instrument for evaluating performance of teachers of electrical installation and maintenance works in Science and Technical Colleges in north-eastern states of Nigeria. Ezekiel reported that 126-items were found

appropriate and required for evaluating performance in electrical installation and maintenance works. In the same vein, Okwelle and Okoye (2012) who developed and validated an instrument for assessing practical skills in building electronics systems in Nigerian technical colleges found out that 61 practical skills were appropriate for the ESSAS. To further buttress the findings, Asukwo, Akpan, and Yusuf (2019), Akpan et al. (2019), Asukwo et al. (2019), Mbaga, Yusuf and Asukwo (2022), Hassan, Musa and Usman (2020) and Okoye and Auta (2020) who in the separate submissions reported that the content of the developed instrument were appropriate and measure what was supposed to be measured.

The findings of the study on the psychomotor skills task items in the DIPSAT underscore its validity in accurately measuring the intended constructs. This assertion aligns with established principles of construct validity assessment in measurement tools (Anastasi & Urbina, 1997). The study's results are in line with the concept of content validity, indicating that the task items effectively capture the targeted psychomotor skills, confirming their alignment with the intended construct definition (Streiner et al., 2015). Furthermore, the study's assertion of validity is reminiscent of the criterion-related validity concept, as it implies that the task items correlate well with the constructs they are designed to measure, akin to assessing the measurement tool against an established criterion (DeVellis & Thorpe, 2017). Finally, these findings highlight the importance of psychometric assessments to ensure that measurement tools, such as the DIPSAT, accurately represent the theoretical constructs they are meant to evaluate, ultimately enhancing their utility in research and practice (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

The findings of the study revealed that 20 psychomotor skills grouped in 3 clusters were reliable with the reliability index of 0.87 indicate that DIPSAT was reliable. The findings are in tandem with Asukwo, Akpan, and Yusuf (2019), Akpan et al. (2019), Asukwo et al. (2019), Mbaga, Yusuf and Asukwo (2022) and Okoye and Auta (2020) who in their separate submissions reported that the instrument developed by their study was found reliable as it measures what was supposed to measure. Furthermore, Moses et al (2017) who developed an instrument for assessing practical skills in domestic installation processes at the Technical College Level in Yobe State, Nigeria reported that the instrument was reliable with a reliability index of 0.89. Also, the finding was in consonance with the finding of Ombugus (2013) who developed a workshop-based process skill tests in mechanical engineering craft for assessing students in Technical Colleges in Nassarawa State and found out 40 tasks and 305 skill items valid by using table of specifications.

The findings of the study revealed that the developed instrument for assessing Psychomotor Skills in Domestic Installation was highly reliable with inter-rater reliability of 0.868 reliability index. This finding is related to the findings of Adamu (2019) and Ombugus (2013) where kendall coefficient of concordance and Pearson product moment correlation respectively were used to determine the correlation coefficient between raters. After the inter-rater reliability procedures in this study, it was found out that the developed instrument possessed a high inter-rater reliability when compared with findings reported by Yalams (2001) and Adamu (2019) in similar instruments developed. Therefore, these findings have minimized errors such as personal bias, halo effect, logical error, generosity error and central tendency error mostly encountered in rating students' skills.

Conclusion

The major findings of this study serve as a basis for drawing conclusion that Domestic Installation Psychomotor Skills Assessment Instrument is a valid and reliable instrument for assessment that could be used in assessing Electrical Installation and Maintenance students' psychomotor skills in technical colleges. DIPSAT will also enhance the employability skills of students in Nigerian Technical colleges and effectively assess students' performances in practical. In

so doing, the teachers will be able to show proof of the scores and grades that they award. Furthermore, when properly implemented, students' employability skills performance in EIMW will be improved if the DIPSAI is adopted for assessing psychomotor skills in Nigerian Technical Colleges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. DIPSAI should be made available to the Ministry of Education in order for the ministry to make it an instrument to be used in the assessment process of psychomotor skills in technical colleges in Bauchi State
2. Examination bodies such as NABTEB, WAEC, and NECO should adopt the use of DIPSAT for the assessment of students' performance in practical examinations in EIMW trade especially domestic installations.
3. The teachers of Electrical Installation and Maintenance works in Nigerian Technical colleges should be encouraged by Government to use DIPSAT to assess students' psychomotor skills in domestic installations.
4. The developed DIPSAT should be subjected to further try-out by the teachers of Electrical Installation and Maintenance in other geopolitical zones of Nigeria in order to serve as a means of further assuring its efficacy, practical usefulness and eventual adoption for the assessment of psychomotor skills of EIM students at NTC level.

References

- Akpan, G. A., Udoh, A. O., Asukwo, A. E., & Daniel, P. M. (2019). Development and Validation of Psychomotor Skills Assessment Guide for Repairs of Radio Receivers in Electronics Work for Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science, Technology and Vocational Education*, 7(1), 77–99.
- Asukwo, A. E., Akpan, G. A. & Yusuf, M. A. (2019). Scaling-up Assessment Techniques in Technology Education for Sustainable National Development: Development and Validation of Psychomotor Skills Assessment Guide for Diagnosis and Repair of Electronic Circuits in Technical Colleges. *Book of Proceedings of the 3rd Annual International Conference of the International Forum of Educational Benchmarkers, Premier Journal of Education*, 2(1), 55-73. 13th – 17th May, 2019. University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- Asukwo, A. E., Vincent, C., Daniel, P. M. & Michika, M. U. (2019). Development and Validation of Psychomotor Skills Assessment Guide for Repairs of Television Receivers in Electronics Work for Technical Colleges in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark*, 13(2), 10–27.
- Alotaibi, S. M., Albdoor, A. A., & Baddourah, M. A. (2018). Smart home automation system with different levels of integration. *Energies*, 11(11), 3110.
- Anastasi, A., & Urbina, S. (1997). *Psychological testing* (7th ed.). Prentice Hall/Pearson Education
- Angoff, W. H. (2017). Scales, norms, and equivalent scores. In *Educational measurement* (2nd ed., pp. 245-279). American Council on Education.
- Baird, L., Feather, P., & Fisher, T. (2019). Fire hazards in residential electrical installations. *Fire Safety Journal*, 107, 101869.
- DeVellis, R. F., & Thorpe, C. T. (2021). *Scale development: Theory and applications*. Sage publications.
- Ekeh, I. (2016). Quality assurance in technical and vocational education and training in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 8(1), 42-54.

- Ezekiel, S. (2010). *Development of an instrument for Evaluating Performance of Teachers of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works in Science and Technical Colleges in North Eastern States of Nigeria*. Unpublished Ph.D thesis, Federal University of Technology, Yola.
- Hassan., A.A., Musa., H.Y., & Usman., M.Y. (2020). Development and Validation of an Instrument for Assessing Practical Skills in Electronics Works Trade in Technical Colleges in North East Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Scientific and Engineering Technologies Research* (8)(4),30-40.<https://www.seahipaj.org>.
- Ismail, I. A., Yunus, J. M., & Al-Kaf, A. A. (2021). Psychomotor skills development in engineering education: Issues, trends, and the way forward. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 1-18.
- Mann, S., & Shipman, P. (2018). Performance assessment in technical education. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 10(1), 50-63.
- Mbaegbu, C. C. (2018). Challenges of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6(7), 119-130.
- Mbaga, E. V., Yusuf, M. A., and Asukwo, A. E. (2022). Development and Validation of a Psychomotor Skills Assessment Tool for Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade of Technical Colleges in Nigeria. *International Journal of Vocational Studies and Library Science (IJOVALIS)*, 2(2), 1 – 21. <https://benchmarkjournals.com/international-journal-of-vocational-studies-and-library-science-ijovalis/>
- Nkosi, D., Njenda, T. D., & Chikhungu, L. C. (2020). Electrical installation in residential buildings: An overview. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering*, 9(3), 1910-1916.
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H. (1978). *Psychometric Theory* McGraw-Hill New York Google Scholar.
- Ogunbote, F. O., Agunwamba, J. C., & Alake, B. M. (2020). Relevance of technical colleges to the needs of technological development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 9(03), 1516-1521.
- Okoye, K. R. E. & Auta, M. A. (2020). Development and Validation of Instrument for Assessing Students Practical Skills in Building Super-Structure Operations in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 7(2), 1-12.
- Okwelle, P C. & Okoye, K.R.E. (2012). Development and Validation of Instrument for Assessing practical skills in building electronics system in Nigeria technical trends in engineering and applied sciences 3(3). Retrieved May 26, 2022 from <http://www.jeteasscholarlink> research org
- Oladinni, S. T. (2019). Development and validation of an instrument for assessing students' psychomotor skills in basic electricity. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 11(1), 17-26.
- Rodriguez, M. J. (2019). Assessing the psychomotor domain in technical education: A comprehensive framework. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 11(2), 1-14.
- Streiner, D. L., Norman, G. R., & Cairney, J. (2015). *Health measurement scales: A practical guide to their development and use*. Oxford University Press.
- Sulaiman, R., Shah, P. M., Ibrahim, H., & Ahmed, N. (2021). Assessment in technical and vocational education: A review of challenges and solutions. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 13(1), 14-27.
- Wagiran, A., Talib, A. Z., Nek, K. S., & Ramlan, R. (2019). Psychomotor skills assessment in science education: Theoretical framework and empirical evidence. *Creative Education*, 10(09), 2190-2204.
- Wang, H., Yao, L., & Jia, M. (2018). Construction and validation of psychomotor skills measurement in electrical experiments based on the Delphi method. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 590.

Appendix:

DOMESTIC INSTALLATION PSYCHOMOTOR SKILLS ASSESSMENT INSTRUMENT (DIPSAI)

Name of Student:..... Gender :.....

Class:..... Date :..... Duration:.....

Scoring Rubric: Excellent 5, Very Good 4, Good 3, Poor 2, Very Poor 1		RUBRICS				
S/N	Cluster 1: Surface Wiring Tasks	5	4	3	2	1
1	Drawing electrical installation diagram for building					
2	Demonstrating the use of plumb-line					
3	Demonstrating the use of chalk-line					
4	Demonstrating the use of spirit level					
5	Carrying out simple surface wiring					
6	Observing safety measures required in surface wiring					
	Cluster 2: Conduit Wiring Tasks					
7	Identification of conduit components					
8	Identification of types of conduits					
9	Utilization of conduit accessories					
10	Threading conduit pipes using a ratchet handle tool					
11	Carrying out simple surface conduit installation					
12	Carrying out simple concealed conduit installation					
13	Drawing cables into conduit installation using fish wire					
14	Carrying out the inspection of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations					
15	Carrying out the required tests of the conduit installation as required by the IEEE regulations					
16	Maintenance of tools used for conduits installation					
	Cluster 3: Installation of Protective Devices Tasks					
17	Utilization of protective devices					
18	Carrying out connections of ELCBs to the supply authority					
19	Carrying out inspection on joints made in a simple wiring					
20	Demonstrating the use of test lamp					
	TOTAL SCORES OBTAINED					
	<p>Note: Students' score should be converted to 100 marks using the formula</p> $\text{score} = \frac{x}{N} \times 100$ <p>where x= student's total score obtained and N=maximum obtainable score</p>	<p>KEY:</p> <p>70-100 Expert 60-69 Proficient 50-59 Competent 45-49 Advanced Beginner 0-45 Novice</p>				

Competency Level:.....

Teacher's Name:..... Sign and Date:.....